

Convolutional Neural Network for Recognition Bangla Handwritten Words

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ABSTRACT

Convolutional Neural Network has become the advanced stage of technology for image recognition. It has been widely used for offline recognition of handwritten words of different languages such as English, Arabic, etc. This paper proposes a system for recognizing Bengali handwritten isolated characters and words using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The actual purpose of this system is to introduce an automated process that can be used to recognize a particular Bengali handwritten word to find the equivalent machine-readable format of that word. Based on the internal construction of the system, three different recognizing models have been introduced in this experiment. The 2-Layer CNN model, the Pure CNN model, and the 3-Layer CNN model have undergone several evaluation processes throughout the whole experiment to determine a stable model with satisfactory recognition accuracy. The 2-Layer CNN model has the highest accuracy of 72% when trained with the selected dataset. When trained with the same dataset, the Pure CNN model has produced 80% recognition accuracy for only ten epochs and the 3-Layer CNN model has produced a maximum 97% recognition accuracy. The models have also been trained and evaluated using the MNIST and Bangla-Lekha-Isolated datasets.

Keywords:

Bangla Handwritten character, Bangla word dataset, Convolutional neural network, Deep learning, Word recognition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Handwriting has been used as a daily means of communication almost from the start of human evolution towards modern science. Many popular studies and applications have been carried out during the last years, mainly used to process bank cheques, read mailed envelopes, and recognize handwritten text in documents [1]. In recent years, Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) have gained much attention as they can persistently outperform other motions virtually in all the fields of computer vision [2]. Because of their outstanding performance, the convolutional neural model is used highly for handwritten text recognition. However, the use of CNNs in word dotting applications has been decreased. Word dotting is a fruitful prototype to index report images. There are multiple advanced technologies for word dotting, and CNN architecture has been proven to outperform them [3]. As a result, CNN has been used in word dotting in multiple languages, including English [4] and Arabic [5]. There is a variety of handwriting from person to person, so it is very tough to get a satisfactory result of recognition in this field & different handmade features have been used in these identification studies. But in the case of CNN, it automatically detects the features of an image, thus reducing the need for handmade feature set [6]. This is one of the primary reasons CNN is ideal for a language like Bangla,

where there are different writing styles and alphabets, many of whom often look alike, thus making the option of handcrafted feature generation very hard. Approaches to recognizing handwritten text usually consist of various steps, including data preprocessing, feature extraction, classification, and post-processing. However, extracting the feature and designing the classifiers are the two main steps of any recognition system [6]. Recent experiments on CNN have shown their ability in document recognition ploy [6]. From the training character image samples in an unsupervised scheme, these tectonics can learn the feature vector [6]. The proposed system is trained and evaluated using a standard Bengali handwritten character dataset first. For word-level recognition, a dataset with 100 unique Bengali words has been developed, and there are 250 samples for each of the words.

Bengali is one of the most popular languages spoken or used by 220 million people in Bangladesh and India [7]. It is the first language of Bangladeshi people. The tongue holds 50 basic alphabets and more than 24 compound characters complemented, including 10 distinct digits and 10 Shoro-Chinno [8]. This diversity of alphabets and digits has resulted in complex literature with different writing styles. A method that can recognize these writing styles and store them digitally can significantly impact Bangla Literature applications. Multiple research projects have been conducted to generate a

method of recognizing Bangla Handwritten. But most of this research had been focused on character recognition, while no proper research has been conducted on word recognition. This is primarily due to the lack of a proper dataset.

This motivated us to create a model that can recognize handwritten Bangla words. And since there is a lack of a proper dataset on Bangla words, we were also motivated to create a dataset containing some of the most used words in Bangla literature.

This paper is based on Bengali handwritten text recognition using CNN. CNN has been found as a very effective and appropriate approach for Bengali handwritten character recognition. This paper explores the word-level recognition accuracy of different CNN models. Recognizing Bengali handwritten words comprising of composite characters is a challenging task. This proposed system wants to find an efficient solution for this challenge.

Proposing a CNN-based model for Bengali handwritten word recognition is the initial objective of the research. To get the primary goal, the following sub-objectives have been introduced:

- To prepare a basic CNN model and evaluate its performance based on established datasets.
- To prepare a “Bangla Word Dataset” and evaluate its effectiveness using the prepared model.
- To generate multiple models based on some hypothesis and evaluate their performance.
- To propose the best model generated as the Bangla handwritten word recognizer.

The paper has been documented in five significant chapters that include the background analysis of the concept, overview of the proposed system, implementations, evaluation using simulations, and summarizations.

Chapter 2: Literature Review explores the analysis of the background of our proposed model. It offers an overview of past works done on a similar concept. It also shows the different scopes of improvement of these past works incorporated into our model.

Chapter 3: System Overview describes the models that have been created to recognize the Bangla handwritten characters. It also gives a short description of the different layers that form a CNN. And finally, this chapter gives an overview of the datasets used in training and testing the models.

Chapter 4: Implementation Details discusses the steps involved in implementing the model. It presents an insight into the implementation by describing how the dataset had been collected and preprocessed, creating the models, and evaluating the models. This chapter also includes a structural comparison of the different models.

Chapter 5: Experimental Results and Discussions discuss each model's result. Based on these results, a comparison has also been shown. This chapter also describes the impact of several epochs on the validation accuracy. Finally, this chapter shows the relation between the number of layers in a CNN model and the training time required to train such a model.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Future Works summarizes all the steps taken to complete the research. It also discusses the

applications of the different models. This chapter also describes the limitations that had hindered the progress of the research. And finally, it discusses some of the methods to overcome these limitations and ways to modify the scope of the proposed models.

2. BACKGROUND STUDY

2.1 Deep Learning

Deep learning is part of a wider family of machine learning methods based on data representations than task-specific algorithms. [1]. Deep learning models are motivated by information processing and communication patterns in adoptive nervous systems. Still, they have some imparity from adoptive brains' structural and functional properties (especially human brains), which make them patchy with neuroscience testimony [2]. Figure 1 shows a basic neural network model.

2.2 Convolution Neural Network

Convolution neural network (CNN) is a class of deep learning. This is applied mainly for recognizing images, image or video processing, and natural language processing. A CNN is used for both descriptive and generative purposes. A Traditional neural network is either a combination of hardware or software or sometimes both. It was mainly built to mimic the structure of the human neural network, but a traditional neural network is not completely suitable for image processing and image recognition, whereas the model must feed images in reduced Resolution pieces. CNN is a type of artificial neural network designed to process pixel data. The CNN model is organized to mimic the human visual effect in an efficient form. CNN mostly uses multilayer perception. The CNN consists of an input layer, an output layer, and several hidden layers to reduce the processing requirement compared to the traditional neural network. Figure 2 shows the basic CNN configuration.

Figure 1. Neural Network Mathematical Model [14].

Figure 2. Basic Configuration of Convolutional Neural Network [15].

2.3 Advantage of Convolutional Neural Network

Deep learning has efficiently gained impressive visual and speech recognition [16]. The Convolution neural network (CNN) is trained in a supervised way, so while training the network, it must decide which supervised way is required to train [17]. A CNN requires few preprocessing compared to other models. One of the best advantages of a CNN is, it does not require to use handcrafting feature vector. The CNN is trained in a supervised manner; it does not require handcrafting to compute the feature vector. It's because of the design structure of the CNN. It learns its feature vector from the training data set provided in the shape of an image. The CNN is used to train a large class problem. As the CNN is a segment of machine learning so, according to traditional machine learning, it is predicted that the training and testing data set has the same feature distribution [6]. Several text-related applications based on image recognition can be widely sorted to retrieve multimedia, visual input & access, and industrial automation [18].

In web content, especially in images or videos, sometimes it is seen that there is some text on photos or videos that contains important information about the website or the information about some personal interest required to retrieve. In those cases, multimedia retrieval is required to extract the text from the image. [18]. Nowadays, most mobile devices contain a digital camera. For this reason, the imaging device has become widely available. There is some special embedded module in mobile that automatically takes input name cards, whiteboards, and slide presentations. A user can do this stuff without using the keyboard; it has made their working experience comfortable and efficient [18].

2.4 Previous Work

Many previous experiments for handwritten character identification in a different language, such as Latin [30], Chinese [31], and Japanese [32], have had significant success. "A complete printed Bangla OCR system" [33], "On the development of an optical character recognition (OCR)" [34] system for printed Bangla script is some of the publications accessible for Bangla handwritten basic character, digit, and compound character recognition. There are relatively few handwritten Bangla number recognition studies that achieve the required recognition accuracy.

"Automatic identification of unconstrained offline Bangla hand-written numbers" [35], and "A system towards Indian postal automation" [36] are two of Pal et al. research's papers on identifying handwritten Bangla characters. "Touching

numeral segmentation using the water reservoir notion" [37] is another example. The suggested systems are based mostly on characteristics taken from a notion known as a water reservoir. Apart from that, there are other Bangla Handwritten Character Recognition systems that have had a lot of success. Many researcher papers examined numerous techniques to improve the performance of Bangla OCR [38] – [44].

Convolution neural network (CNN) gives an advantage of image recognition, so the advantage is used to recognize handwritten word recognition. The disappointment is that the contribution to Bengali word recognition has not been done previously, and there is no enriched data set. It has been seen that Character or Word recognition falls under two types, namely online and off-line [17]. Among them, online recognition requires special devices to produce words. The primary focus of this paper is on off-line word recognition. Off-Line recognition is done using image classification techniques. Most of this recognition work (both online and off-line) has been done based on English handwritten text recognition. Different approaches for this task have been introduced [2]. These include holistic methods such as Markov Method, which has evolved to Hidden Markov Method (HMM), which is very popular in recent times; analytic methods with explicit segmentation, such as character segmentation, implicit segmentation, etc., the hybrid method such as pre-classification methods, reducing context with increasingly detailed diagnostics, etc. But no detailed experiment has been done on word-level recognition of Bengali handwritten words based on these models. The primary reason for this is the lack of a dataset. That is where CNN comes to play. CNN is a dynamic approach to image processing that can work well, even on a small dataset [20]. Previous processes regularize CNN at the fully connected layer or spatial-pooling layer [21]. However, we concentrate on the convolutional layer. Some research has also presented a CNN structure trained with the PHOC deputation.

CNN-N-Gram for Handwriting Word Recognition has also been used previously. Offline cursive Bengali word recognition has also done recurrent acting model. Paperwork in the Indian sub-continent has been carried out on database generation of the basic handwritten character of Bengali, and a model has been developed for recognizing similar Bengali characters, which uses two-step classification. Modified Quadratic Discriminant Function (MQDF) classifier and multilayer perception [7]. Recently research has been carried out on Bengali letter and digit recognition using a deeper residual network [22]. Another model for Bengali character recognition was used, a hierarchical model for optical character recognition for Bengali handwritten words, which follows the 2-step process. 1st it uses a hierarchical approach to segment characters from the words, and in the next stage, it uses multilayer perception for classification. In this model, maximum accuracy was 93.90% for 35 classes of words [8].

But this paper has been done on the core Convolution neural network (CNN) model that recognizes the handwritten words from images without segmentation. The accuracy of our

proposed model is up to 96%. And the number of classes that it can classify is 100.

3. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

In this paper, a model has been designed that can predict a handwritten Bangla word. The model has been designed after tinkering with different configurations of Convolutional Neural networks (CNN). This chapter focuses on the architecture of the proposed model and why this model has been chosen.

3.1 Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a genus of a deep learning network that is most notably used in visual imagery analysis. The model offers a lot of advantages over its peers because it generates very accurate predictions for a relatively low amount of training data. Another advantage to using CNN is that it requires no or very little handcrafted feature vector. As a result, the model designed using CNN can gain a huge performance boost with image processing in terms of processing and analysis. CNN models are easier to train and can perform well with fewer parameters than the traditional fully connected layers, which is proven by how CNN can be used to gain almost human-level accuracy when trained and tested with the MNIST digit recognition task [23]. The reduced requirement in terms of parameters also contributes to reduced training time. The operation of a CNN is like the traditional computer vision mechanisms. In both cases, filters are used to extract certain features of an image, but in the case of a CNN network, the filters are not generated manually. This results in less human interaction. Since the filters or features are not predetermined, a single CNN model can be trained with different training datasets to learn different things. Instead, the model decides upon the features to best solve the task.

A CNN model remains one or more Convolutional Layers (CL), and in most cases, these layers are pursued by a form of Pooling Layer. But there are some unique CNN models, such as the pure Convolutional model, which consists of a CL one after the other, with only a Global Pooling layer at the end. Other layers present in the model are Flatten layer, dense layer, and dropout layer. Any layer other than the Convolutional and pooling layer is collectively called the Fully Connected Layer. Besides the Convolutional and Pooling layer, the dropout layer impacts the model's accuracy [22]. The job of the dropout layer is to minimize over-fitting as much as possible. Figure 3 gives a distinct view of how the different layers are connected to form a convolutional network.

Figure 3. General Configuration of a CNN Model [24].

The layers that have been used for creating these models are described as follow:

3.1.1. Convolutional Layer

This is the most significant layer of a CNN structure. Image analysis generally uses a 2D Convolutional Layer (CL). 2D CL have been used to create the model. It is used to apply filters of predetermined shapes. The layer divides the image into multiple small parts for a single input image using filters. Each filter results in multiple outputs. And each layer implements multiple filters. Therefore, the total number of inputs for the fully joint layer increases significantly. To reduce the overall size of the number of parameters to be used for calculations, these inputs are then fed to a Pooling layer and, in some cases, the dropout layer. The input shape of a 2D CL is a 4D tensor with shape (batch, rows, cols, channels). This type of input is called the channel last input since the channel has been presented last among the four inputs. Channel first is another input pattern. But in both cases, the calculations remain the same. The output is another 4D tensor of the form (batch, new rows, new cols, filters). Suppose it is considered that the CL is of the volume W . In that case, the filters are applied in the image one after the other with a stride (the number of pixels the filter shifts after each filtering) $S = 1$ is the default value. The Filter or Kernel size = K . Amount of 0 paddings is P , then the volume of output is:

$$O = \frac{W-K+2P}{S} + 1$$

3.1.2. Pooling Layer

The pooling layer is another important layer of the CNN model. It is a form of down sampling that receives input from the convolutional network. In the simplest terms, it applies a pooling filter to determine the pixel value that most successfully represents the region within the filter. Then it replaces all the pixels within the filter with the pixel value that had just been calculated. This results in fewer parameters to be received by the fully connected layer for processing. The pooling layer thus reduces the input parameter without hampering the quality of the input. The input and output of the "Pooling" layers are like that of the CL. A 2D "Max-Pooling" layer is the most common form of pooling layer used in 2D image processing. In a max-pooling layer, the maximum pixel value within a filter region is

used to replace the entire region covered by the filter. Another type of pooling used is the “Average-Pooling” layer. The average value of pixels within the filter region replaces the entire filter region in an average. Figure 4 shows how a Max-Pooling layer downsamples a $4 * 4$ image to a $2 * 2$ version.

Figure 4. Operation of a Max-Pooling Layer

3.1.3. Dense Layer

This is the third most important layer of the CL, after the CL and the pooling layer. This layer is the primary building block of the “fully connected” layer, and it is used to do the final calculation after many convolutions and pooling layer has been passed. It generally receives input from the last pooling layer. Then it generates a random filter to identify the input. At the first epoch, the selected filter is not very accurate at identifying the input. But with each epoch, the dense layer tries to make a less inaccurate filter than the previous epoch. This method of reducing error is called “Gradient Decent”. These filters are then used to predict the testing image to determine the label of the image. The label also represents the class of the image.

3.1.4. Dropout Layer

This layer is used for reducing overfitting the model. It takes a value between 0 and 1 as input and cuts the input into size accordingly to decrease the number of parameters and memory leakage. But the perimeter value must be selected very carefully, as too much cutting of the inputs may result in the “Dense layer” not having enough parameters and therefore reducing the quality of the filters it generates. On the other hand, if very little input is cut off, the dense layer will have more inputs than necessary and result in complex shapes filters instead of simple filter shapes capable of identifying generic shapes. The ideal dropout ratio is between 0.2 and 0.6, but it depends on the input dataset. The final model was used as a dropout of 0.2. This ratio is intentionally kept small because the dataset size is small. Therefore, too much dropout is not necessary.

3.1.5. Other Layers

A combination of the layers discussed so far is generally all that is needed to create a proper CL. But some other layers are often used to make the models more optimized. Some of the different layers used are Flatten, Activation Layer, etc. A special layer is used in a Pure Convolutional is the GlobalAveragePooling2D() layer. It is a type of “Average-Pooling” layer. The advantage of using a “Global-Pooling” is that it can receive input of any size and not just a fixed size like the local versions discussed earlier.

3.1.6. Gradient Descent

The various parameters, such as the shape of the filters, the internal calculations of the fully connected layers, etc. are done in a gradient descent manner, in which the computer begins calculation using some random values for the parameters and gradually goes in the direction that generated the most promising outputs. And as a result, the accuracy of the first few iterations is very low, but as the number of iterations increases, the model also keeps getting more accurate.

3.2 Models

Using different configurations of these layers, the following models have been created and tested, with each model showing significant improvement compared to the following:

- 2-layer CNN model
- 8 Layer Pure CNN model
- 3 Layer CNN model

All these models have been tested on three distinct datasets. Firstly, each of them has been tested on the MNIST dataset, a popular dataset that contains a huge collection of English characters. Then the model was tested on the “Bangla Lekha Isolated”. It is a huge dataset containing 84 classes, where 50 of them are for basic Bangla letters, 10 classes are of numerals, and 24 classes are for compound letters. We had created the third dataset as a word-level dataset.

3.2.1. 2 Layer CNN Model

This model consists of 2 pairs of CL and Max-Pooling layer. This model had been designed with the idea that the more layers there are, the longer it will take to train a model, but the model would be a lot more accurate. But since the primary goal at this stage was to test if the “Bangla Word Dataset” had been efficiently preprocessed, a model with only 2 CLs had been modeled. When the model was tested on the “Bangla Lekha Isolated”, the model returned a validation accuracy of near 70%. And therefore, the validation accuracy benchmark needed to decide if the preprocessed dataset is useable or not had been set to 70%. Apart from the obvious Convolutional and Max-Pooling payers, the other basic models had also been used to create the fully connected network part of the model. The model had was trained and tested using only 10 classes of data.

Different experiments were done on the database to figure out the most efficient values of the different parameters used while designing the future models. The original model had a beginning filter size of $28 * 28$ pixels. The size was changed to different values to identify the relation between the input dimension, learning time, and learning accuracy. The increase in the input dimension showed improvement in the overall accuracy, but the model took longer to learn the patterns. The model had also been trained using image augmentation. And this did improve the training accuracy. The best input dimension and initial filter size were $128 * 128$ pixels and $26 * 26$ pixels. This combination allowed us to reach the benchmark validation accuracy. But the accuracy was still too little, and thus this model had been further modified. Augmentation of the dataset was also done to train the model to recognize words from different angles. The batch size of the augmentation was

64. The training of this augmentation required a long amount of time, and the accuracy had also suffered. That is the reason the augmentation approach had not been considered throughout the experiment. The summary of the model is shown in model 5.

In [3]: model.summary()

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 26, 26, 32)	320
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2)	(None, 13, 13, 32)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 11, 11, 32)	9248
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2)	(None, 5, 5, 32)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 800)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 100)	80100
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 100)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 10)	1010
activation_1 (Activation)	(None, 10)	0
Total params: 90,678		
Trainable params: 90,678		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 5. A 2 Convolutional Layer Payer Model Summary

3.2.2. Convolutional Layer

A pure CNN model is a unique model. This model had been designed with nine consecutive CLS with no form of pooling layers in between. The model was based on the observation that the inclusion of more CLs improves the model's overall performance, and a single pooling can be set globally to do the downsampling at the end of each successful epoch. Removing the pooling layers also meant that the total number of layers would be reduced to almost half the original size. This made it possible to include more CLs. The model had shown that the validation accuracy had increased to almost 79% to 80% for about only 10 epochs when trained with the image of 64 * 64 pixels. But the model had not been considered for further modification since training this model would require a lot more computational power and time (Almost 4 hours for a single epoch) than the previous model. And hence, the original 2 Layer CNN model had been chosen for further modification. This model had also been trained using an input size of 56 * 56 pixels. But to reduce the runtime, the size was reduced to 32 * 32 pixels. The details of the summary model are present in Figure 6.

In [3]: model.summary()

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 32, 32, 96)	960
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 32, 32, 96)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 32, 32, 36)	31140
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 16, 36)	11700
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 16, 16, 36)	0
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 16, 192)	62400
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 16, 192)	331968
conv2d_6 (Conv2D)	(None, 8, 8, 192)	331968
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 8, 8, 192)	0
conv2d_7 (Conv2D)	(None, 8, 8, 192)	331968
activation_1 (Activation)	(None, 8, 8, 192)	0
conv2d_8 (Conv2D)	(None, 6, 6, 192)	331968
activation_2 (Activation)	(None, 6, 6, 192)	0
conv2d_9 (Conv2D)	(None, 6, 6, 100)	19300
activation_3 (Activation)	(None, 6, 6, 100)	0
global_average_pooling2d_1 (	(None, 100)	0
activation_4 (Activation)	(None, 100)	0
Total params: 1,453,372		
Trainable params: 1,453,372		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 6. A Pure CNN Model Summary

3.2.3. 3 Layer CNN Model

This model has been designed to modify the original 2 Layer CNN model directly. It introduced a new payer of CL and MaxPooling Layer. The model also introduced a dropout layer between the second and the third payer. The value of the dropout ratio was kept to 0.5. The model at first showed an increase in both validation accuracy and training accuracy, 87%, and 82%, respectively. But this accuracy was still unacceptable. The initial size of the input images was 56 * 56 pixels. But increasing the input size allows the model to learn from more variables, thus increasing the learning accuracy [22]. Therefore, the input image size was increased to 64 * 64 pixels. This increase in size had shown that the testing accuracy had increased to almost 92%, but the validation accuracy was way behind with only 85% accuracy. The pixel size had been further increased to a size of 124 * 124. And this increase in the input image size had resulted in a slight increase of both testing accuracy (95%) and validation accuracy (87% to 89%). But the increase in the image size also resulted in more computation time. An experiment on the Bangla Lekha Isolated had shown that decreasing the dropout size would substantially increase the validation accuracy [22]. Therefore, the ratio had been decreased to a value of 0.2. The output model had resulted in a validation accuracy of almost 97%. But since the model now has more data to learn from. Therefore, the input image size had to be shrunken to 64 * 64 pixels. The model had no significant change in terms of validation accuracy even after the reduction in size. The model was then trained using the total number of

100 classes of images. And even with this huge number of different input images and classes, the validation accuracy had only reduced to 96%. After experimenting with varying sizes of input, the model that had been chosen is summarized in Figure 7.

3.3 Bangla Word Dataset

Dataset for this paper consists of a collection of 100 common Bangla words. Table 1 shows the words. The words are classified into four general types. They are:

- 24 words with two letters.
- 26 words with three letters.
- 25 words with four letters.
- 25 words with compound letters.

250 samples of every word have been recorded for training from 25 different writers. Each writer has been given 10 different special areas for writing the same words to ensure minimal word replications. The words had been selected based on the overall popularity of the words in everyday Bangla literature.

The words of this data set have been selected based on the everyday uses of these words in day-to-day Bangla literature.

4. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The implementation of the model had been done in 4 stages:

- Gathering the dataset
- Preprocessing the dataset
- Creating the model
- Evaluation of the model

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In [10]: model.summary()
...:

```

layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 62, 62, 32)	320
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 31, 31, 32)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 29, 29, 32)	9248
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 14, 14, 32)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 14, 14, 32)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 12, 12, 32)	9248
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 6, 6, 32)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 1152)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 100)	115300
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 100)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 100)	10100
activation_1 (Activation)	(None, 100)	0

```

Total params: 144,216
Trainable params: 144,216
Non-trainable params: 0

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Figure 7. A 3 Convolutional Layer Payer Model

Table 1. The Words Included in the Dataset.

2 Letter	3 Letter	4 Letter	Compound Letter
বই	ইফাস	মেহমান	ডাক্তার
রবি	ঈগল	রমজান	মেধার
চিনি	আংটি	দেলোয়ার	কুমিল্লা
ঢাকা	বোতল	আবদার	অম্মান
ছিপ	কমলা	গাড়িয়াল	অক্ষর
চাল	খেলনা	চাঁদপুর	অজ্ঞ
ডিস্কি	গমন	রংপুর	বিস্ত
রাজা	ভ্রমন	অনুযায়ী	অভিজ্ঞ
রানী	দালাল	শয্যাগত	প্রতিক্ষা
মালা	নর্দমা	প্ররোচনা	পঞ্চমুখ
ঘড়ী	শায়লা	অবিরাম	অনির্দিষ্ট
বর্ণ	বিহার	পরিমিত	নষ্ট
শশী	ঘরোয়া	যোগফল	অশ্ব
চুপ	বাংলা	ক্রমাগত	নশ্বর
দিন	বাঙলা	পুরাতন	পঞ্চগন্ন
ছবি	চিংড়ি	দীর্ঘকাল	উদ্ধত
তুমি	ইলিশ	সহযোগী	অক্ষন
আমি	বৈশাখ	পরমাশু	হবিগঞ্জ
বাজে	শ্রাবণ	ভাইরাস	চট্টগ্রাম
পথ	আষাঢ়	প্রতিরোধ	নিরক্ষর
ঝিল	আমড়া	প্রভাবিত	শ্রীলঙ্কা
মূর্তি	কিতাব	চিংকার	সম্পর্ক
উষা	ময়ূর	আপতিত	বিশ্ব
রাঙা	পিঁপড়া	সবচেয়ে	সম্মেলন
	দোলনা	শারীরিক	রোহিঙ্গা
	কাঁঠাল		

The flowchart of the model is shown in Figure 8, where the four steps mentioned above are discussed.

Figure 8. Flow Chart of the Model Implementation

4.1 Gathering the Dataset

The primary dataset used for training the model was generated by making a list of some of the most frequently used words in Bengali literature. The data had been gathered from a total of 250 different individuals. Everyone was provided with a sheet. The sheet had a space to write the letters. They had been instructed to keep the words within the space allocated for writing each word. The space had been procedurally generated so that writers would find random angles for the words. This was done because, in real-time, the handwritten text is not always aligned to a certain axis. So, with data from different angles, the trained model would be more accurate at identifying texts that are not prerecorded. The dataset was then manually separated, and each entry was renamed in the following format, W_xW_y . Here W_x stands for the X^{th} writer, and the W_y stands for the Y^{th} word. Each word had been kept in the folder designated for them. The dataset intentionally contains very few ambiguous words, such as “BABA” and “KAKA”, since the alphabets required for the two words in Bengali literature are very similar.

The dataset contains four primary groups of data. Words with two letters, three letters, four letters, and finally words with compound letters. Another critical factor that had to be considered while collecting the dataset was the term “Matra”. In Bengali literature, the absence of matra or the placement of matra can change the letter and thus the word. So, special care had to be taken to ensure that the writer correctly followed the implementation of matra. To avoid confusion regarding the

correctness of spelling, all the spellings had been checked as per the “Bangla Academy” standard. If there are multiple spelling for the same word, only one of the spellings had been included in the dataset, except for the word “Bangle”. There are two ways one can write the word “Bangla”, and both the words had been used as a different class in the dataset. The words were manually separated from the image containing different images. And since the images in the next step would get resized, the cropped images had been saved in PNG format for lossless resizing [9]. The graphical representation of the word collection and words separated is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Gathering Individual Words from the Source

4.2 Preprocessing the Dataset

Preprocessing means preparing the dataset for training the model. The data gathered in the previous step has some flaws that would greatly hinder the model's performance if they had not been preprocessed beforehand. This is because the raw dataset has noise. Noise can be interpreted as unwanted information, such as the color of the sheet or the shadow that the device had cast while taking pictures of the collected words. And each image of the dataset is of a different size. The model cannot deal with datasets, where each data is of a different size. So, the images also had to be resized to the same dimension. The dimension also had to be kept at optimal size since keeping the value too small would result in the image going lower in quality while keeping the value too high, the model would take too long to get trained. The different dimension that has been used in this experiment is $56 * 56$ pixels, $64 * 64$ pixels, $128 * 128$ pixels.

128 pixels, etc. The raw data was in RGB format. An image in RGB format has three different color channels. “Red”, “Green”, “Blue”. But the model had been designed to handle a single channel of the color. Therefore, the image had to be converted to binary. But since RGB cannot directly be converted to Binary, it must be converted to grayscale first. After the images had been converted to grayscale, they had been converted to binary. The gray to binary conversion was performed using Otsu’s Method [25] to select the best threshold value for basing the conversion. Once each image had been converted to binary, it had been flattened to convert the 2D image into a 1D array to make the model readable. The process is shown in Figure 10.

Afterward, an array had been declared. The size of the array was equal to the number of images in the input dataset. Then a loop was used to set a value to each of the values in the attributes’ elements accordingly. These values had been used as labels of the dataset. After labeling, the dataset was shuffled randomly to ensure that a data set was not clustered together. Then the labels were converted to categorical data [26]. This was done for faster access to the labels, as now the labels could be represented using only a single bit. Then the dataset was split into two groups—one for training and another for testing. The split had been done using the “train_test_split” function. A parameter was used in the “train_test_split” function named “test_size=0.1”, which indicates that out of every 100 data from the dataset, 10 were to be used as the testing 90 had to be used as the training data.

Figure 10. An Image Before and After Preprocessing

4.3 Creating the Model

The model had been created using the Keras library. Keras is an open-source neural network library capable of running on Tensorflow and Theano. [12]. The model is a sequential one. It has a linear stack of layers. A sequential model implements each layer in a sequential manner per epoch. The model can be trained using a Numpy array of input data. The function add() had been used to add layers to the model. The output of one layer would act as the income of the following layer. The activation function used on the convolution layers is rectified linear units “ReLU”. “ReLU” activation function has been used because research has shown that this results in much faster training for larger networks [27]. And for the activation of the entire model, a “softmax” activation has been used. Although this is optional, using its yield in the benefit that instead of resulting in either 0 or 1, the model can now calculate how close the testing data is to a specific training data. 0 stands for no resemblance, and 1 means the two data are the same. Any value within 0 and 1 is also possible. And the result is displayed in categorical format. Therefore, comparing the results to the testing labels also becomes easier. The entire model has been implemented using Anaconda.

The first layer added to the model is the Convolution 2D layer. Its first parameter, “Filter Number” indicated the number of filters used in the input image. Each of the filters generated a set of outputs. These outputs are then sent to the next layer, the Maxpooling2D layer. The Maxpooling2D layer has a 2 * 2 filter. This filter is used to down-sample the input and generate output with a reduced number of variables. This pair is repeated one more time. The number of these parameters is reduced by using the dropout layer to avoid overfitting. Then another Convolution 2D and Maxpooling 2D had been implemented. These convolutional and pooling layers resulted in many small images taken by the fully connected layer.

The primary task of the fully connected layer is to compare the miniature inputs with filters that will get more refined with every epoch. In other words, given a set of input images, the fully connected layer tries to create filters that detect the layers as accurately as possible. The accuracy of these filters is the so-called training accuracy. A fully connected layer creates these filters by way of Gradient Descent. Gradient Descent is a form of reinforced learning [28], where the goal is to move towards lower errors with every epoch. The primary building block of the layer is the “Dense” layer. The task of the dense layer is to connect all its nodes with all the nodes of the layer that comes before and after the “Dense” layer. The flatten layer also prepares the data for input into the dense layer. Then there is another dropout layer that reduces overfitting once again. A second “Dense” layer trains the model a bit faster. The model is then compiled. The compile function has the parameters, “loss”, “optimizer”, and “metrics”. Loss calculates the errors during the training, and the optimizer learns the weights and matrices that define what the evaluations are based on, such as accuracy.

Once the model has been made, it is trained using the “model.fit()” method. The method takes as input the training data and their labels. The number of epochs is also set in this part. It is set to 200.

4.4 Evaluation of the Model

The model had been evaluated in three steps. Firstly, the model had been evaluated as it had been trained. This evaluation used the testing data as the validation data. The validation data had generated the “Validation Accuracy” and the “Validation Loss”. This evaluation method is optional, but the method has been working as the primary evaluation mechanism while testing the different models. The way this validation is accessed is by informing the “*model.fit()*” function that it has also to evaluate the model alongside training it by adding the optional parameter “*validation_data = (x_test, y_test)*” [11].

Secondly, the model had been tested using our testing data. In this approach, the model.*predict()* function was used to predict the model's label. These labels were then compared with the list containing all the labels of the testing dataset using the matplotlib library. Matplotlib was also used to plot the change in validation loss per epoch and the validation accuracy per epoch. Once all three tests had been met, the second evaluation form started. Two different plots had been used to evaluate the model.

- Plot the “Accuracy” and “Validation Accuracy” for every epoch
- Plot the “Loss” and “Validation Loss” for every epoch

Figure 11. Accuracy of the Model Plotted Per Epoch.

Figure 12. Loss of the Model Plotted Per Epoch

Table 2. Results of the 2 Layer CNN model

Dataset	Number of Class	Input Size (Pixels)	Validation Accuracy
MNIST Dataset	10	28 * 28	85%
Bangla Lekha Isolated	10	28 * 28	70%
Bangla Word Dataset (Raw)	10	28 * 28	40%
Bangla Word Dataset (Preprocessed)	10	28 * 28	68%
Bangla Word Dataset (Preprocessed)	10	128 * 128	72%

Figure 11 provides a graphical representation of the model getting more accurate with every epoch classifying a given image or word. On the other hand, Figure 12 provides a graphical representation of the reduction of the loss value with every model.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter the experimental result is discussed. First the 2-Layer, 3-Layer, and pure layer CNN model are discussed with their accuracy in this model. Then the comparison is discussed at the last.

5.1 A 2 Layer CNN Model

Since this model had not been built for the accuracy of the prediction but rather for the evaluation of the model, it has the lowest accuracy of the three models. The model had initially been trained using images of size 28 * 28 pixels. This model had originally been tested on the “MNIST” dataset. The validation accuracy of the “MNIST” dataset was around 85%, even on this low-quality model. Then the model was trained using 10 classes of data from the “Bangla Lekha Isolated”. The validation accuracy this time was only around 70%. This showed that the model should not be used for recognition purposes. Then the model was trained using the unpreprocessed version of our own Bangla Word Dataset. The validation accuracy was even lower to the point of 40%. Then after different preprocessing steps discussed earlier had been taken, the results had reached 66% to 68%. After some modifications to the data fed to the model, the accuracy had gone to almost 72%, thus confirming the reliability of the

Table 3. Results of the Pure CNN model

Dataset	Input size (Pixel)	Time per epoch	Validation Accuracy
Bangla Word Dataset	128 * 128	Above 7 hours	Training Skipped
Bangla Word Dataset	64 * 64	3 hours	80% (Only 10 epoch)
Bangla Word Dataset	56 * 56	2.5 hours	78% (Only 10 epoch)
Bangla Word Dataset	32 * 32	1 hour	74% (Only 10 epoch)

Table 4. Results of the 3-layer CNN model

Dataset	Number of Class	Input size (Pixel)	Drop Out Value	Validation Accuracy
Bangla Word Dataset	10	56 * 56	0.5	82%
Bangla Word Dataset	10	64 * 64	0.5	85%
Bangla Word Dataset	10	64 * 64	0.2	97%
Bangla Word Dataset	100	64 * 64	0.2	96%
Bangla Word Dataset	100	128 * 128	0.2	97%

model. Table 2 details the results of the different experiments done on the model.

5.2 A Pure Layer CNN Model

This model had been trained using different pixel volumes of the preprocessed version “*Bangla Word Dataset*”. The model has not been trained using the other datasets since our dataset had already proven reliable. The model had 9 Convolutional layers. Therefore, the accuracy of this model was a lot improved. But due to there not being sufficient pooling layers, the model had a lot of validation loss and could not be trained using larger-sized images. This model had also been trained using only 10 classes. The experimental result of the model is shown in Table 3.

5.3 A 3 Layer CNN model

This model is a modified version of the original 2-layer model. Its growth towards validation accuracy is a bit slower compared to the Pure CNN model. But its time per epoch is very small (12 to 15 minutes). Therefore, this model sacrifices the learning growth per epoch for the time per epoch. The model had been trained with different image sizes and dropout values. This is the first model to be trained using 100 different data classes. Different experimental results of the model are shown in Table 4.

In this model, the input with the image size of $128 * 128$ pixels had shown huge improvements in the case of validation accuracy. But it did have a bit more validation loss due to overfitting. Compared to that, the input size of $64 * 64$ pixels showed almost similar results. And therefore, the final model had been trained using images of this size.

5.4 Discussion

As stated in the previous section, all the models have pros and cons. They highly depend on the purpose of the model. For example, the 2-Layer model had very poor accuracy. But the model was successful at helping us to determine its usability of the model. As discussed in section 4.2, with each modification to the dataset, it had been tested to see if the dataset was preprocessed enough.

On the other hand, it has also been discussed that the learning rate of the pure CNN model is better than the model

Table 5. Comparison of the outputs of the 3 models

Model Type	Number of Input Classes	Input Size (Pixel)	Number of Epoch	Time per Epoch	Validation accuracy
2 Layer CNN model	10	128 * 128	80	<1 minute	72%
Pure CNN Model	10	64 * 64 (128 * 128 skipped)	10	3 Hours	80%
3 Layer CNN Modell	10	128 * 128	80	4 to 5 minutes	97%
3 Layer CNN Modell	100	128 * 128	200	12 to 15 minutes	97%

used for the final testing. And as for the final model, it gives a quality performance, even though it has a slow learning rate. As seen in Table 2, raw images are not suitable for the training of the models. This is because raw images contain a lot more additional information. They can be measured more accurately using a 3-channel model. But that would require a more powerful machine to train. To train the 3 Layer model, 200 epochs were used. But as seen in Figures 11 and 12, the required amount of epoch is a lot less. But the optimal number of epochs varies every time the model is trained. And therefore, many epochs have been selected. Table 5 shows a disparity of the best outcomes of the three models. The table depicts the number of epochs needed for the training, the number of classes trained using the model, the accuracy gained, the size of the image, and the time it took per epoch.

Table 5 also shows that when training using the same parameters, the time required per epoch increases almost exponentially due to the inclusion of an additional Convolutional and Pooling payer. The new payer generates multiple filtered images for a single input from the previous layers, thus increasing the number of learnable parameters. With this, the estimated time for each epoch needed to train a Pure CNN model with 10 classes of images with an input size of $128 * 128$ pixels would be around 2^8 minutes or more than 4 hours. Therefore, it can be estimated that the time required for training all 100 classes would be even higher. Thus, the model had been skipped.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper shows an offline optical character recognition (OCR) method known as Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to recognize handwritten bangle words. CNN is one of the most broadly used neural network methods for visual perceptions. The model can be used in any of the fields of visual perception, but its most notable use lies in the field of image analysis. The results prove that a CNN model with relatively fewer layers can also perform well given a good enough dataset.

The experiment is like other methods that involved recognition of Handwritten Bangla Characters. However, most of these experiments had been done using a large dataset. But our experiments also introduced a new dataset that contains some of the most frequently used Bangla words.

The experiment was based on three CNN models. Each of the models had their pros and cons. These models had been tested using multiple evaluation methods that proved the quality of the models. And at the end, a tradeoff had to be made between learning rate and learning time, and the faster model had been picked as the final model. And although the model was a little less accurate than the most accurate amongst the three proposed models, it reached its accuracy in very little time. And the least accurate model had also been used to establish a benchmark accuracy for datasets. This benchmark can be used in other reasserts to estimate the effectiveness of newly established datasets. This benchmark had been established using the popular digit dataset, named the MNIST dataset. Two different compressions tables were used to compare the three models. One table had been used to show the difference in the construction of the three models. And the other table compared the results that each model would produce for the same dataset.

Different limitations stopped us from creating a much deeper model during the model's training. These limitations include hardware limitations and the limitation of a rich dataset. The limitations of hardware resources had been overcome using overclocking. But the major limitation was that there is no established dataset of the different Bangla words to be used. So, the dataset had to be made from scratch. But due to different environmental constraints, the created dataset did not have sufficient data. Our dataset consists of only 250 images of each word, divided into a 9:1 ratio for training and testing. That had left us with only 225 images for training the data per class. The “*MNIST Dataset*” consists of 6000 training images for a single class and 1000 testing data for that class. As a result, their training and testing results were much more accurate. This lack of sufficient data was, however, overcome by sophisticated preprocessing. But the impact of a lack of dataset had been made obvious during the real-time testing, where the model did not have enough data to keep up with the constantly shifting image. The dataset also lacks in terms of class. There are thousands of words in Bangla literature. But our model can only recognize only 100.

The first recommendation for future work regarding the system is to increase the data size for each class or word so that the model can be fed more data and make it more accurate. Modifications to the system are also recommended to recognize data presented in real-time. Since the model is limited to identifying only the 100 classes it has been taught; a more dynamic approach can be applied to identify each of the characters, the spacing, and the applications of “matra”, and then dynamically determine the words. That way, any number of words can be trained. Alternatively, the model can be taught to learn even more data classes. But either of the cases will require more layers to be added to the model. A dynamic approach can increase the number of layers while minimizing the average time per epoch. This method is called the RESNET [29]. The reason for not using this model is that our models were not too deep to consider such a dynamic approach. But to

train the model with more classes or make it more dynamic in word recognition, it is crucial to increase the number of layers. And at that point, the RESNET model should be applied [29]. The further system can also be modified to recognize entire sentences. Once the “*Bangla Word Dataset*” is rich enough, steps could be taken to merge the “*Bangla Lekha Isolated*” dataset and the “*Bangla Word Dataset*” to form a unified Bangla dataset.

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REFERENCES

1. Arica, Nafiz, and Fatos T. Yarman-Vural. “An overview of character recognition focused on offline handwriting.” *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)* 31, no. 2 (2001): 216-233.
2. LeCun, Yann, and Yoshua Bengio. “Convolutional networks for images, speech, and time series.” *The handbook of brain theory and neural networks* 3361, no. 10 (1995): 1995.
3. Sudholt, Sebastian, and Gernot A. Fink. “Phocnet: A deep convolutional neural network for word spotting in handwritten documents.” In 2016 15th International Conference on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition (ICFHR), pp. 277-282. IEEE, 2016.
4. Yuan, Aiquan, Gang Bai, Lijing Jiao, and Yajie Liu. “Offline handwritten English character recognition based on convolutional neural network.” In 2012 10th IAPR International Workshop on Document Analysis Systems, pp. 125-129. IEEE, 2012.
5. Elleuch, Mohamed, Rania Maalej, and Monji Kherallah. “A new design based-SVM of the CNN classifier architecture with dropout for offline Arabic handwritten recognition.” *Procedia Computer Science* 80 (2016): 1712-1723.
6. Maitra, Durjoy Sen, Ujjwal Bhattacharya, and Swapan K. Parui. “CNN based common approach to handwritten character recognition of multiple scripts.” In 2015 13th International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR), pp. 1021-1025. IEEE, 2015.
7. Bhattacharya, Ujjwal, Malayappan Shridhar, Swapan K. Parui, P. K. Sen, and B. B. Chaudhuri. “Offline recognition of handwritten Bangla characters: an efficient two-stage approach.” *Pattern Analysis and Applications* 15, no. 4 (2012): 445-458.
8. Basu, Subhadip, Nibaran Das, Ram Sarkar, Mahantapas Kundu, Mita Nasipuri, and Dipak Kumar Basu. “A hierarchical approach to recognition of handwritten Bangla characters.” *Pattern Recognition* 42, no. 7 (2009): 1467-1484.
9. Sayood, Khalid. *Lossless compression handbook*. Elsevier, 2002.
10. Culjak, Ivan, David Abram, Tomislav Pribanic, Hrvoje Dzapo, and Mario Cifrek. *A brief introduction to OpenCV*.

- In 2012 proceedings of the 35th international convention MIPRO. IEEE, 2012.
11. Abadi, Martín, Paul Barham, Jianmin Chen, Zhifeng Chen, Andy Davis, Jeffrey Dean, Matthieu Devin, et al. "{TensorFlow}: A System for {Large-Scale} Machine Learning." In 12th USENIX symposium on operating systems design and implementation (OSDI 16), pp. 265-283. 2016.
 12. Chollet, François. "Keras: Deep learning library for theano and TensorFlow." URL: <https://keras.io/k> 7, no. 8 (2015): T1.
 13. Hunter, John D. "Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment." *Computing in Science & Engineering* 9, no. 03 (2007): 90-95.
 14. Karpathy, Andrej. "Neural networks part 1: Setting up the architecture." Notes for CS231n Convolutional Neural Networks for Visual Recognition, Stanford University. <http://cs231n.github.io/neural-networks-1> (2015).
 15. Peng, Min, Chongyang Wang, Tong Chen, Guangyuan Liu, and Xiaolan Fu. "Dual temporal scale convolutional neural network for micro-expression recognition." *Frontiers in Psychology* 8 (2017): 1745.
 16. Wu, Chunpeng, Wei Fan, Yuan He, Jun Sun, and Satoshi Naoi. "Handwritten character recognition by alternately trained relaxation convolutional neural network." In 2014 14th International Conference on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition, pp. 291-296. IEEE, 2014.
 17. Poznanski, Arik, and Lior Wolf. "Cnn-n-gram for handwriting word recognition." In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, pp. 2305-2314. 2016.
 18. Ye, Qixiang, and David Doermann. "Text detection and recognition in imagery: A survey." *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 37, no. 7 (2014): 1480-1500.
 19. Sun, Qinpei, Yuanyuan Yang, Jianyong Sun, Zhiming Yang, and Jianguo Zhang. "Using deep learning for content-based medical image retrieval." In *Medical Imaging 2017: Imaging Informatics for Healthcare, Research, and Applications*, vol. 10138, pp. 270-280. SPIE, 2017.
 20. Wang, Tao, David J. Wu, Adam Coates, and Andrew Y. Ng. "End-to-end text recognition with convolutional neural networks." In Proceedings of the 21st international conference on pattern recognition (ICPR2012), pp. 3304-3308. IEEE, 2012.
 21. Adak, Chandranath, Bidyut B. Chaudhuri, and Michael Blumenstein. "Offline cursive Bengali word recognition using CNNs with a recurrent model." In 2016 15th International Conference on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition (ICFHR), pp. 429-434. IEEE, 2016.
 22. Alif, Mujadded Al Rabbani, Sabbir Ahmed, Aleo Aninda, and Tanoy Kumar Das. "Isolated Bangla handwritten character & digit recognition using convolutional neural network." Ph.D. diss., BRAC University, 2017.
 23. Ciregan, Dan, Ueli Meier, and Jürgen Schmidhuber. "Multi-column deep neural networks for image classification." In 2012 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, pp. 3642-3649. IEEE, 2012.
 24. Jing, Luyang, Taiyong Wang, Ming Zhao, and Peng Wang. "An adaptive multi-sensor data fusion method based on deep convolutional neural networks for fault diagnosis of planetary gearbox." *Sensors* 17, no. 2 (2017): 414.
 25. Otsu, Nobuyuki. "A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms." *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics* 9, no. 1 (1979): 62-66.
 26. Agresti, Alan. "Two Bayesian/frequentist challenges for categorical data analyses." *Metron* 72, no. 2 (2014): 125-132.
 27. Krizhevsky, Alex, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey E. Hinton. "Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks." *Advances in neural information processing systems* 25 (2012).
 28. Baird, Leemon, and Andrew Moore. "Gradient descent for general reinforcement learning." *Advances in neural information processing systems* 11 (1998).
 29. Wang, Fei, Mengqing Jiang, Chen Qian, Shuo Yang, Cheng Li, Honggang Zhang, Xiaogang Wang, and Xiaoou Tang. "Residual attention network for image classification." In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, pp. 3156-3164. 2017.
 30. Kavallieratou, Ergina, Nikos Liolios, E. Koutsogeorgos, Nikos Fakotakis, and G. Kokkinakis. "The GRUHD database of Greek unconstrained handwriting." In Proceedings of Sixth International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition, pp. 561-565. IEEE, 2001.
 31. Yin, Fei, Qiu-Feng Wang, Xu-Yao Zhang, and Cheng-Lin Liu. "ICDAR 2013 Chinese handwriting recognition competition." In 2013 12th international conference on document analysis and recognition, pp. 1464-1470. IEEE, 2013.
 32. Zhu, Bilan, Xiang-Dong Zhou, Cheng-Lin Liu, and Masaki Nakagawa. "A robust model for on-line handwritten Japanese text recognition." *International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJDAR)* 13, no. 2 (2010): 121-131.
 33. Chaudhuri, B. B., and U. Pal. "A complete printed Bangla OCR system." *Pattern recognition* 31, no. 5 (1998): 531-549.
 34. Pal, Umapada. "On the development of an optical character recognition (OCR) system for printed Bangla script." PhD diss., Indian Statistical Institute-Kolkata, 1997.
 35. Pal, U., and B. B. Chaudhuri. "Automatic recognition of unconstrained off-line Bangla handwritten numerals." In *International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces*, pp. 371-378. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2000.
 36. Roy, Kaushik, Szilárd Vajda, Umapada Pal, and Bidyut Baran Chaudhuri. "A system towards Indian postal automation." In *Ninth International Workshop on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition*, pp. 580-585. IEEE, 2004.
 37. Pal, Umapada, A. Belaid, and Ch Choisy. "Touching numeral segmentation using water reservoir concept." *Pattern Recognition Letters* 24, no. 1-3 (2003): 261-272.
 38. Dutta, Abhijit, and Santanu Chaudhury. "Bengali alpha-numeric character recognition using curvature features." *Pattern Recognition* 26, no. 12 (1993): 1757-1770.

39. Pal, Umapada, and B. B. Chaudhuri. "Indian script character recognition: a survey." *Pattern Recognition* 37, no. 9 (2004): 1887-1899.
40. Bhowmik, Tapan Kumar, Ujjwal Bhattacharya, and Swapan K. Parui. "Recognition of Bangla handwritten characters using an MLP classifier based on stroke features." In *International Conference on Neural Information Processing*, pp. 814-819. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2004.
41. Mashiyat, Ahmed Shah, Ahmed Shah Mehadi, and Kamrul Hasan Talukder. "Bangla off-line handwritten character recognition using superimposed matrices." In *Proc. 7th International Conf. on Computer and Information Technology*, pp. 610-614. 2004.
42. Bhattacharya, Ujjwal, Malayappan Shridhar, and Swapan K. Parui. "On recognition of handwritten Bangla characters." In *Computer vision, graphics and image processing*, pp. 817-828. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2006.
43. Chowdhury, Ahmed Asif, Ejaj Ahmed, Shameem Ahmed, Shohrab Hossain, and Chowdhury Mofizur Rahman. "Optical Character Recognition of Bangla Characters using neural network: A better approach." In *2nd ICEE*. 2002.
44. Forkan, Abdur Rahim Md, Shuvabrata Saha, Md Mahfuzur Rahman, and Md Abdus Sattar. "Recognition of conjunctive Bangla characters by artificial neural network." In *2007 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology*, pp. 96-99. IEEE, 2007.

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